

Environmental Implication of Livestock Development

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Abstract

This paper attempts to elucidate the diverse environmental implications of livestock development. This paper aimed at examining and highlighting the types of livestock management system to bring out the environmental implications; with a view to fully understand the complexity of each system.

Keywords: *environmental implications, agriculture, livestock, pastoralist, farmers*

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Introduction

In the process of raising the general standard of living of its people various governments of developing and developed nation have pursued policies on Agriculture, Industrialization, Transportation and on exploitation of national resources for a better and more meaningful life without being mindful of the need to strike a healthy balance between our development pursuit and a quality environment; because forever development and no matter the how small development is, there is a corresponding environmental degradation or changes in what the environment use to be (FAO, 1974).

Amongst, this developmental effort is the developing of livestock industry- an integral part of Agriculture, which in an integrated economic activity upon which over several millions of farmers and pastoralist derives their livelihood. The development aims at ensuring efficient production, raising productivity, promoting animal and human health and ensuring adequate and equitable return to producers. The industry has a significant role in the socio-economic development of nation, as source of food of animal protein origin for animal and human consumption, provider of manure,

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cultivation of farm land, serve an insurance against crop failure and use as a measure of social status amongst the traditional livestock rearers.

The main objective of this paper is to review the sources of environmental degradation and problems due to the development of livestock sub-sector in Agriculture.

Livestock Products and It's by Products

The term livestock refers to animal kept on farms and other biting insect and creature so, on broad economic sense, livestock includes domesticated and wild animal that are used for human consumption. The main agricultural animals of the world are, cattle, sheep, pig, and goat, buffalo, horse, ass and mule of course including poultry. These agricultural animal could in turn be grouped as ruminant and non-ruminant. Other animals that are of considerably important in livestock development, but not common as human food or have more or less economic significance are Cat, Dog, Monkey etc which are generally refers to as "Pet".

However, livestock industry also involved production of primary products and or by products such as meat (poultry, beef, pork, mutton), milk eggs, hides and skins for leather industry, draftpower and transportation, dung for manure and fuel, and offals and bones for the industries, others include production of milk products, like curd, cheese, yoghurt, butter and ghee, chhena and khoa (made in Asia), condense milk, dried milk and ice-cream. In addition to these are hair, Wool, Hooves, Horns, blood, Gases, heat, methane and urine.

System of Livestock Management

The environment in which livestock is introduced are physical and human environment. The physical environment includes the land (soil), atmosphere, and others. Living and non-living things occurring in space.

Livestock industry occurs under different management systems and the effect of these various system on the environment would be highlighted in this section. The systems of livestock management are (a) Extensive management system (b) Intensive management system (c) Semi-intensive management system, this falls in between the other two.

Extensive Management System

This system is well practiced and almost dominated by the traditional Nomadic cattle rearers in most Africa countries such as the West, North east, East Africa, than the

Continental J. Agricultural Science

Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

Western Asia. The major features of this system is that animals are led to moving around in search of grazing and water and or left on their own to roam about the bush and street in search of pasture or scavenging for food materials.

In the wake of this migration, the animal's transverse many lands leading to varying results and consequences such as the destruction of crops and pollution of drinking water. This condition often leads to serious conflict between pastoral nomads and sedentary farmers, as it was evidenced in Kano and Plateau State (Awe and Doma Local Governments).

In addition to this, the movement of cattle under this system enhances the spread of many zoonotic diseases, i.e. the diseases that are infectious and naturally transmitted between Animal and man, and Animal to Animal. Zoonoses constitute an important component of the whole public health field and are one of the most important areas of veterinary public health activities. Among the zoonosis recognized today are Anthrax, Brucellosis, Tuberculosis, Rabies and Several of the more arthropod borne viral infection such as Tick borne relapsing fever (WHO, 1974).

The following are some of the Zoonotic diseases.

Anthrax

This is also called wool sorte disease for the germs used to be hidden in wools, hides and skins. In man this disease can show as localized postules. People at risk include livestock farmers, people working in abattoirs and health personnel including laboratory staff.

Brucellosis

Brucellosis is a disease of cattle, goat and sheep caused by a causative agent called Bovine melitensis which is highly virulent for man. WHO (1974) gave a stock ton of estimation of about 350 million U S dollars annually and that substantial members of human cases of incapacitating illness had been reported in America alone.

In fact, most of the infectious of man that have been discovered in the last 20 years are shared with lowers animals and a number of diseases previously thought to be limited to man have been found to be Zoonoses (WHO, 1974).

The method (Mode of infection) by which Human beings can contact these diseases are usually by unknowingly eating (ingesting) the causative germ (Bacteria or Virus) either

Continental J. Agricultural Science

Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

by eating with dirty hands or breathing in the germs (aerosol droplet method) e.g. tuberculosis.

Moreover, the traditional livestock rearers often goes about with their bows and arrows for hunting purposes and such hunting activities also are particularly responsible for the destruction of wild animals that are in fact a part of balance of Nature. Cattle utilize the plant that is desirable to the recreationist from an aesthetic point of view. Littering of better camp site, in their transient nature along the stream is an unacceptable source of contamination couple with the smell and offensive nature of their droppings.

Roaming of livestock in the street has often caused destruction of flowers, bed in many homes, destruction of valuable properties especially in market areas, where loosed animals are often seen entering into stalls to eat traders' good and foodstuff. In addition, goats, sheep and cattle are often seen crossing roads at random and arbitrary and as such they often caused accidents on the roads claiming lives.

Though, the extensive range land grazing system provides the cheapest source of feed for livestock, but the dangers is that with the increasing pressure from other competitive land use, the grazing land diminishes and this gives rise to over-concentration of livestock on land with the attendant problem of trampling, leaf defoliation and of course, overgrazing.

Grazing is complex system that involves soils, plants and animals interacting with factors to govern their behaviour. In such a system the physical factors, plant and animals function as a unit and any changes in one factor, such as caused by grazing or drought changes the whole complex (Noy - Mein, 1975). With over-grazing, undesirable effect such as disappearance of forage occur as this lead to exposition of soil to erosion, reducing soil productivity and consequently changes the original plant community. The evidence of this effects can be observed in Northern part of Nigeria especially in Sokoto, Kano and Borno where overgrazing has resulted in the gradual changes of the original plants to low value forage plant such as *Cassia tora*, *Waltheris americana*, *Acanthospermum hispidum* (Kallah, 1982).

Intensive System

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The livestock producer of the past had operated largely and almost independently of other segments of the population because there was little population pressure, consequently, he was far from urban centres, but the position has changed drastically as

Continental J. Agricultural Science

Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

a result of the rapid population increase. The inordinate rapid growth in population has proportionately increased the demand for open space and as well as a voice in how this space might affect their lives, therefore considering this and the animal protein needs vis-a-vis poor productivity from extensive management system, the traditional system of livestock production has to give way to intensive system of production in order to meet the ever increasing demand for animal protein.

The notably feature of the intensive system is the fixed building, where the livestock are kept in confinement with the provision of all essential infrastructure like water supply, pasture development, road, fencing, high plane of nutrition etc. However, high intensity livestock production satisfies the need to improve the efficiency of livestock management and to exploit the genetically constituents of livestock through application of technology in the principle of livestock nutrition and disease control. But rather than removing the environmental impact, it has increased the extent of it. It is under this system of livestock production that the technological innovation feedlot operation (Ranching) and poultry houses are classified.

The changes to confinement of livestock have magnified deforestation and production of animal waste such as excreta. The disposal of wastes from the system has developed into a major problem in recent years particularly, in the developed nations of the world where livestock production is done on a very large scale. Though excreta is used as manure, but however, in some instances the area of land available may be inadequate and climatic and topographical feature may restrict the amount of excreta that can be applied, thus a varying amount of it is lost from the system as run-off, when it rains, into the surface and underground water (Vukina, 2001).

For instance, the run-off feedlot and chicken dropping has been reported to contain Managanese (Mn) and Zinc (Zn) which can locally contaminate surface water and shallow under ground water. Other wastes (organic) that constitute additional resources within land economy in the system are silage liquor that may seep away during processing and conservation of herbage. Though the actual wastes handle depends upon the stock variation, feed variations, drinking water system, cleaning and budding methods.

In another study, an increase in Nitrogen (N₂) from 2mg/litre to 15mg/litre has been reported in a run-off as it flowed under a barn yard. Chicken manure has also been reported to be the sources of organisms causing human respiratory diseases caused by

Continental J. Agricultural Science
Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

fungus *Histoplasma capsulatum*, the pathogen is air borne from dry dropping chicken manure. The most common of local environmental impact which often may be regarded as small nuisance but, which can in some circumstances causes considerable distress are (i) Flies (ii) Odour (iii) Noise (iv) Effluent - such as slurry which however, could be used as fertilizer and at the same time serve as disease and parasites transmitter . Vukina (2001) also reported that, the increase in fly population in California is ascribed to livestock concentrations that have moved nearer the cities and also to residential expansion towards the farm with their new livestock practices.

A report from the independent commission on international humanitarian issues has it that 38% of deforestation in Brazil between 1966 and 1975 was due to ranching. In another, reports, it was said that almost three quarter Brazil cleared forest is used for cattle ranching and that an area of 2 million hectares is cleared each year for the purpose of supplying cheap meat (Beef) for export to North America. This view is equally supported by (Williamson and Pyne, 1978).

Intensive system of livestock involves the use of drugs and chemicals in food production and such drugs has associated problem of drug residue especially with copper and arsenic containing drugs. This then bring about the issue of food hygiene in respect of the dairy industry, abattoir and livestock feed mill - developed as subsidiary industries from intensive system of diversity production. Food hygiene is concerned with the conditions and method of production, processing, storage and distribution and aims at ensuring safe and wholesome products fit for human consumption. Food borne pathogen such as *Vibrio parchaem* has been recognized.

Dairy Industry

The major product from dairy industry is milk and milk products that are consumable. Other products that can be classified as waste includes waste water from the cleansing of the milking machine and parlour, corn, and boxes that may constitute nuisance to the environment, if, they are not properly disposed or discharged to avoid draining into soil by percolation and seepage into groundwater. Human beings, however, could be infected by Tuberculosis through milk, especially raw milk if taken. The waste water from Dairy industry measure as oxygen consumption (BOD) has been reported to be three to four times more polluted than household wastes water.

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Abattoir

Slaughter house by products arising from the slaughtering of livestock includes Blood, Bones, Horns and Hoofs and water from the cleansing of the slaughtered animal and slaughter house floor. Though quite a number of these products have now been put into productive use, however, the only danger there is that, of disposal of them adequately because, they can equally constitute nuisance and eye sore in the environment.

Feed Mill Plants

These are allied industries developed from intensive system of livestock production. These plants produce concentrated feed for animal production. Some of the pollutants from the industry may include dust and fumes, effluent discharge, suspended solid, and thermal pollution.

Environmental Management in Livestock Industry

Livestock production base consists of renewable resources that must be sustained against degradation and such resource includes range land, soil, water, of course human and livestock generation sources. However, efforts have been geared up in most Countries of the world towards the establishments of grazing reserves as a response to the deleterious effects of traditional system of livestock production. In some of these grazing reserves, pasture were developed and partition into paddocks so that livestock can graze on rotational basis among there paddocks, to prevent overgrazing which might result into soil erosion or extinction of plant species. This measure however, many reduce the spread of transmission of diseases from animal to animal and from animal to man.

Yet there is no single method generally satisfactory for the treatment of the animal manure originating in confinement livestock operation. Methods that have, however, been employed in most cases include field spreading as manure, composting, lagooning, incineration and possibly the dehydration of the excreta. As a matter of fact, it is pertinent to say here that animals droppings has been incorporated on a lower level into poultry feeding as a source of protein feed and biogas production.

Conclusion and Recommendation

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The environmental impact of extensive, intensive and livestock base industry have hitherto not been fully appreciated in most developing countries especially in Nigeria. Hence, the information which is available in this topic is rather scarce. Therefore, there

Continental J. Agricultural Science
Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

should be conscious efforts towards creating awareness in area of environmental pollution or implication of livestock production.

Intensive animal production and industrial food processing have given rise to problems of waste disposal, pollution of water, air, and soil on which man survival on earth depends. Therefore, efforts should be geared up towards the reduction or elimination of these various environmental hazards.

Finally,

1. A comprehensive animal and human health care delivery service should be established.
2. More grazing reserves land should be established with adequate provision of infrastructure for the existence ones.
3. Veterinarians should be adequately encouraged and equipped because; they play a key role in the field of maintaining sanitary hygiene at slaughter houses, farm houses and associated industries.
4. There should be strict enforcement of the existing legislation regarding all matters of Animal and Human Health.

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Continental J. Agricultural Science
Adedeji (2019) 13 (1): 24 - 32

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